

INDUSTRIAL DEVELOPMENT CONTRIBUTES TO THE GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT IN BIHAR

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Abstract:

The economy of Bihar is largely service oriented, but it also has a significant agricultural base. The state also has a small industrial sector. It is known that agricultural growth is 23% in 2012-2013. Bihar's economic growth is 14.48% in 2012-2013 as shifting from agricultural sector to tertiary sector. Bihar has the lowest GDP per capita in India but there are pockets of higher per capita income like the southern half of the state and its capital city, Patna. Bihar's GDP grew by 11.03%, which made Bihar the second fastest growing economy in India during that 5 year period, just behind Gujarat's growth of 11.05%. For industrial development, the government has cleared a total of 135 proposals worth Rs 71,289.64 crore, submitted by big entrepreneurs for setting up medium and large industries. related to sugar mills, ethanol, engineering and medical colleges and power production in the state. A sum of Rs 602.54 crore had already been spent on various activities pertaining to the cleared projects, which are likely to create job opportunities for over 114,000 people. The proposals include opening of 23 new sugar mills and the expansion of seven existing ones, apart from the production of ethanol in two sugar mills and five sugarcane juice production plants. The projects regarding five power plants, 12 food processing units and 15 steel processing and cement plants have also been cleared by the state. Bihar has registered highest growth rate of 14 percent in the industrial sector during nine years period of 2004-2012 among BIMARU category states -Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan and Uttar Pradesh. The dependency of the state government on agriculture does not surprise because Bihar as a state failed in the past to qualify for the industries requirements. The industry set up requires huge infrastructure supports like uninterrupted power supply, availability of land, well connectivity and quality roads/highway, organized markets and good governance etc. An agro-industrial policy will attract investment in the food processing industry in the state. as there are extremely rich in raw materials like fruits, vegetables, milk cereals which could be processed as food products like pickles, sauce, ketchup, dehydrate vegetables and other products.

The objective of the paper is to develop industries in Bihar for development, growth & employment opportunities etc as there are many fertile land, natural resources' and manpower after considering past trends and present scenario, for the benefit of the future.

Key words: BIMARU, GDP, Agro-industrial policy.

INTRODUCTION:

The economy of Bihar, despite global meltdown and slower growth of the overall Indian Economy was able to continue its growth momentum in 2012-13. In spite of moderate deficit in rainfall, particularly during the south-west monsoon, the economy is likely to register a high growth performance in the current fiscal (2013-14) also. This

strong growth process, together with the success of various welfare programmes of the state government, has now created a new atmosphere of confidence in Bihar. It is, therefore, not surprising that the development of the state has drawn attention not only in India, but outside the country as well. With the support of the central government through transfer of more financial resources, particularly a higher award from the 14th Finance Commission, Bihar could continue its growth momentum, gradually narrowing the gap between the state and the national average. For industrial development, the NDA government has cleared a total of 135 proposals worth Rs 71,289.64 crore, submitted by big entrepreneurs for setting up medium and large industries. The proposals are related to sugar mills, ethanol, engineering and medical colleges and power production in the state. A sum of Rs 602.54 crore had already been spent on various activities pertaining to the cleared projects, which are likely to create job opportunities for over 114,000 people. The proposals include opening of 23 new sugar mills and the expansion of seven existing ones, apart from the production of ethanol in two sugar mills and five sugarcane juice production plants. The projects regarding five power plants, 12 food processing units and 15 steel processing and cement plants have also been cleared by the state.

If we focus on the recent data of state's income, we come to know that the economy of Bihar has grown steadily during the period (2006-13). During the period 1999-2006, the economy had grown at an annual rate of 5.7 percent at constant prices. This was the period immediately after the bifurcation of the state in November, 2000. However, the economy witnessed a turnaround due to the policies pursued by the state government thereafter and, as a result, the annual growth rate was much higher at 12.0 percent during 2006-13 period. One can, therefore, term the recent growth process as a 'revival of a stagnant economy'. During this period, the investment level had also increased substantially. From an average annual plan size of Rs. 4200 crore during the Tenth Plan period (2002-07), the average plan size climbed to more than Rs. 16,700 crore during the Eleventh Plan period (2007-12). Besides the size of the investment, the pattern also has undergone major changes, with considerable emphasis now on infrastructural development and social delivery system.

For a proper understanding of the challenges facing in Bihar's economic development, it should be kept in mind that, with a population of 104.0 million in 2011, Bihar is a densely populated region, with no less than 1106 persons living per sq. km. of its area. As per the Planning Commission figures, in 2009-10, 53.5 percent of its population lived below the poverty line in Bihar. Nearly nine-tenths of its population lives in the villages, where the poverty ratio is higher at 55.3 percent. Bihar had to overcome all these challenges to move ahead in a new growth path. Bihar falls in the Gangetic basin area with fertile alluvial soil and abundant ground water resources. With the bifurcation of the state, the vast mineral sector and other big industries went to Jharkhand. The present Bihar was left with only agriculture to depend upon. But with a prudent development strategy, the state could overcome these challenges. The state is now experiencing a development process that is not only very strong, but inclusive as well. The present economic survey has also shown in detail the current status of the state's economy, as well as its various sectors. The sectoral analysis highlights the efforts made by the state government for the different sectors and their respective achievements.

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The state is known to manufacture pulses, shoes, schooter, masur, chasra, electrical good and cotton yarn. The state exports these manufactured products as well as vegetables, purval, and milk. Patna is a major importer of cotton, iron, foodgrains, rice, wheat, wool, and dalhan. Rice accounts for more than one third gross area sown. Other important foodgrains grown are maize, pulses and wheat. Non-food crops consist mostly of oil-seeds, cash crops such as vegetables, water-melons etc., are also grown in Diara belt.

OBJECTIVE:-

The objective of study is to show how industry helps to develop Bihar's economic financial and socio-economic position.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:-

Methodology is the science dealing with principles of procedure in research and study. Research methodology deals with the definition of the research problems, research design, and method of data collection, sample design, statistical tools employed and interpretation of data. The primary and secondary data are used for study with the help of questionnaire, journal, magazine and Bihar development report card 2013.

INTERPRETATION:-

1. If we focus on the below mentioned table (3.4), we can have an idea that though the percentage of industry's share of Bihar is very low with respect to that of India, but it is on the growing stage gradually.

Table 3.4 : Annual Survey of Industries (2009-10 and 2010-11)

Characteristics	2009-10			2010-11		
	India	Bihar	Percentage share of Bihar	India	Bihar	Percentage share of Bihar
Number of Factories	158878	1919	1.21	211660	2807	1.33
Fixed Capital (Rs. crore)	1352184	4452	0.33	1607007	5262	0.33
Working Capital (Rs. crore)	387745	951	0.25	620363	2471	0.40
Total Persons Engaged (No.)	11792055	86620	0.73	12694853	106213	0.84
Value of Output (Rs. crore)	3733036	2825	0.76	4676217	36051	0.77
Net Value Added (Rs. crore)	592114	2321	0.39	704576	4415	0.63

Source : Annual Survey of Industries, 2009-10 and 2010-11

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Bihar has registered highest growth rate of 14 percent in the industrial sector during nine years period of 2004-2012 among BIMARU category states -Bihar, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan and Uttar Pradesh - and even above the average industrial growth at national level, said a study conducted by industry body ASSOCHAM. "This growth is possible because of the continuous contribution of the industrial sector, as shown in the above Table.

2. It is observed from the below table(3.3) that the industrial growth in Bihar has improved but some sectors especially the mining and quarrying, construction and the electricity sectors are not at par the expectation. Hence if such sectors are given financial aids and proper guidance by the government from time to time then the more contribution of industrial sector towards the GDP of Bihar will be possible.

Table 3.3 : Annual Growth Rate of Industrial Sector in Bihar

Sector	Annual Growth Rate		
	2010-11	2011-12	2012-13
Mining and Quarrying	-1.4	-1.5	0.0
Manufacturing	22.8	8.9	9.6
Registered	63.1	17.7	18.0
Unregistered	4.8	2.8	3.0
Construction	34.4	9.9	21.1
Electricity, gas and Water Supply	3.0	8.5	8.9
Total Industry Sector	28.4	9.5	17.1
State domestic product (Rs. 000 crore)	130.27	144.15	165.02

Source : Directorate of Economics and Statistics, GOB

3. From the below mentioned table (3.13), it is known that registration of the medium, SSI, Tiny/micro's is uneven. But they have drastically reduced in 2013-14 due to various reasons like scarcity of electricity, unavailability of proper infrastructure facilities and law and order situation etc.

Table 3.13 : Yearwise Micro, Small and Medium Registered Units set up in Bihar

Year	Medium	SSI	Tiny/ micro	Total	Investment (Rs. crore)	Investment per unit (Rs. lakh)	Employment (in No.)	Employment per unit
Upto 2006-07		1433	162063	163496	801.15		536890	
2007-08	4	42	7156	7202	134.83	1.87	19963	2.77
2008-09	7	25	6122	6154	118.86	1.93	17474	2.84
2009-10	2	41	5048	5091	128.64	2.53	16011	3.14
2010-11	3	33	4799	4835	185.57	3.84	17365	3.59
2011-12	2	56	3904	3962	385.64	9.73	16079	4.06
2012-13	3	53	3681	3737	253.85	6.79	10894	2.92
2013-14, upto September	6	13	457	476	200.95	42.22	9823	20.64
Total	27	1696	193230	194953	2209.40	1.13	644499	3.31
CAGR	-12.8	10.1	-12.6	-12.4	22.4	-	-8.7	-

Source : Department of Industry, GOB

Note: Since 2008-09 artisans have been merged with micro units

4. From the below table (4.34) it is observed that deficit of electricity is more or less same from 2007 to sept, 2013 inspite of some steps taken by the Govt.. As we know that Electricity plays an important role to set up industries, improvement of this sector is very much important for the development of Bihar along with industrial development. So, Government should take more beneficial steps and decisions for privatization and PPP model for improvement of electricity.

Table 4.34 : Power Supply Position in Bihar

Year	Peak Demand (MW)	Peak Availability (MW)	Deficit (MW)	Deficit (%)
2007-08	1,800	1,244	556	30.9
2008-09	1,900	1,348	552	29.1
2009-10	2,200	1,508	692	31.5
2010-11	2,250	1,664	586	26.0
2011-12	2,500	1,712	788	31.5
2012-13	2,650	1,802	848	32.0
2013-14 (Sept. 2013-present)	3,150	2,190	960	30.5

Source: Bihar State Power Holding Company

5. Against the backdrop of emerging positive trend in the industrial sector during the year 2013, Bihar registered an even better achievement. The contribution of Bihar's industrial sector to its Gross State Domestic Product (GSDP) has been increasing during 2009-10 to 2011-12; but it is still smaller compared to any other state.

6. The GSDP of Bihar at 2004-05 prices in 2012-13 worked out to Rs. 165 thousand crore, in which the annual growth rate of industrial sector was 17.1 percent. After registering a setback in growth rate (9.5 percent) in 2011-12, the industrial sector in Bihar appears to be on recovery path, with a growth rate of 17.1 percent in 2012-13. However, it is still lower than the level of 28.4 percent achieved in 2010-11.

7. In Bihar, the total number of MSMEs was around 1.95 lakh by September, 2013. During 2007-08, as many as 7202 units under MSME were registered. However, the number of units registered showed a decline in 2011-12 when only 3962 units were registered. In 2012-13, the number was still smaller at 3737. However, the investment and employment per unit have registered a phenomenal increase over the period.

8. There are in all 28 sugar mills in the state, either under public or private sectors, of which 12 are working. Of the 12 sugar mills, 10 are in private sector and 2 under public sector, both handed over to HPCL in 2011 on lease basis. A total of 35.88 lakh quintals of sugar was produced in 2012-13, compared to 45 lakh quintals in the previous year. The sugar industry in the state is faced with the challenge of low sugar recovery from cane at 8.59 percent, which is much lower than Maharashtra's rate of 12 percent.

9. In terms of milk procurement, Bihar is among the leading states in the country. The number of milk cooperative societies organised upto 2012-13 was 13,681, of which 10,96 were Women's Cooperative Societies.

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The total membership of the dairy cooperative societies was 7.59 lakh in 2012-13. Through these societies, the total milk procured during 2012-13 was 12.45 lakh kgs./day. Against the procurement of 12.45 lakh kgs. of milk/day in 2012-13, the average milk marketing was 9.20 lakh kgs. per day.

10. Handloom units are operational in the state in large numbers which provide employment to around 1.32 lakh weavers. There are 1089 primary handloom societies, with around 10,850 handlooms operating under them and, at the apex level, there are two marketing organisations viz., Bihar State Handloom Cooperative Union and Bihar State Wool and Sheep Union, both located at Patna. The handloom units are concentrated in 14 districts in the state. Under powerloom sector, there are more than 11,000 looms, which are mostly concentrated in Bhagalpur, Gaya and Banka.

11. Till September, 2013, the State Investment Promotion Board (SIPB) has approved a total of 1362 proposals for establishment of industrial units in the state, involving an investment of Rs. 2.83 lakh crore, with employment potential of 2.01 lakh persons. Of the total approved proposal, 56 percent are for food processing and power plants, constituting around 8 percent of the total proposals.

12. The big business houses have already started investing in the state for creating industrial ambience in the state, but more investments are required for faster growth of industrial sector. The state has thrown open many opportunities for the entrepreneurs in various sectors like manufacturing, food processing, tourism, dairy, IT, sugar, tea, and other sectors. The agro-based industries would be a great success in the state because of its agriculture-based economy.

CONCLUSION & SUGGESTION:

From the above observation we come to know that industrial development in Bihar helps to increase its GDP, employment opportunities, national income, improving cost of living of the people of Bihar, socio-economic development through corporate social responsibility ect. It also helps to change the mentality of the people of Bihar and other states about the cultural of this area. Automatically crime is reduced due to employment opportunities and good socio- economic environment is created. Now many industrialists from other states and abroad are interested to set up industries for observing profitability area as this state is now in development state. Besides there are vast availability of natural resources (water, land, etc) and cheap labour. But some areas of the Bihar will be improved for the industrial sector only if Infrastructural, electricity, law and order will be improved. Also, Subsidy is to be given to the industrialist. Red tapism need to be reduced as it takes more time to clear the proposal and start up and it will increase the cost of the project due to time gap.

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Yojna

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